

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE LINGUOCOGNITIVE APPROACH IN THE TEXT ANALYSIS IN THE ERA OF GLOBALISATION AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

In the era of globalization and digital transformation, the development of text analysis based on linguistic-cognitive approaches and the role of language in reflecting cultural and cognitive processes are explored. This article focuses on identifying semantic and pragmatic layers of text, uncovering cultural codes, and developing new methodologies using digital technologies with examples from the Uzbek language. The research results offer broad opportunities in linguistics, education, and cultural studies.

Keywords: Text analysis, linguistic-cognitive approach, globalization, digital technologies, Uzbek language, semantics, pragmatics, cultural codes.

At the present stage of the development of linguistic science within the framework of the anthropocentric paradigm, many scientists most often consider linguistic units in linguocognitive and linguocultural aspects, which form the two dominant approaches in research on the problems of cognitive linguistics. Cognitive linguistics is currently one of the fastest developing and most promising areas of modern linguistics. In the era of globalization and digital technologies, the importance of language has increased dramatically, requiring innovative approaches in the field of text analysis. Digital technologies open up opportunities for deeper understanding of social, cultural and cognitive processes through texts. On the other hand, the linguocognitive approach makes it possible to study language structures not only as linguistic units, but also as tools in the process of forming human thinking and encoding information. This article is devoted to the study of the importance of the linguocognitive approach in text analysis in the context of globalization.

The linguistic-cognitive approach, as the name implies, involves the analysis of not only linguistic, but also cognitive aspects of communication. The linguistic-cognitive approach allows us to identify and analyze two main ones. communication plan:

- 1) the general linguistic aspect (relevant for any communication, any discourse, any language, any language in which communication is carried out);
- 2) the nationally determined component (relevant for national discourse, determining the national specifics of the latter).

In other words, this approach allows, on the one hand, to analyze the universal in communication, to carry out a comprehensive analysis and structure communication, taking into account all the factors that influence communication and determine its course, and on the other hand to identify and explore the national in communication, to identify and describe the national-specific components of communication, because it makes it possible to identify and to investigate the phenomena that reflect the main features of the national mental and linguistic complex and, consequently, determine the national specifics of communication itself.

New possibilities of text analysis using materials from the Uzbek language and international studies are opening up. Research questions:

1. What new approaches does the linguocognitive approach to text analysis offer?
2. How will the dynamics of language systems change in the era of globalization and digital technologies?
3. What are the advantages of analyzing texts in Uzbek based on a cognitive approach?

This research is based on a qualitative analytical method.

The sources of information are:

1. Theoretical research in the field of digital linguistics and cognitive linguistics.
2. Algorithms and programs for text analysis (for example, natural language processing (NLP) tools).
3. Corpus linguistic data for comparative analysis of texts in Uzbek and other languages.
4. Linguistic research of Uzbek scientists and their contribution to the global analysis of the text.

In the course of the analysis, the influence of linguistic units on the cognitive structure, levels of meaning and cultural codes of texts were analyzed. With the help of special programs, the texts were studied semantically and pragmatically.

1. The role of the linguocognitive approach in text analysis

The linguocognitive approach helps to identify semantic and pragmatic layers in text analysis. For example:

* Semantic structure: synonyms and polysemous words in Uzbek have different meanings in different contexts. For example, the word "bright" may reflect meanings such as "shining," "clear," "encouraging."

* The pragmatic layer: the analysis of illocution (purpose) and perlocution (influence) in texts is effectively carried out, in particular, through messages on social networks.

2. Changing language systems in the context of globalization Language interaction on digital platforms is growing. For example:

* The widespread use of foreign words in Uzbek, such as "trend", "content", and "digital", adds new facets to textual culture and analysis. A cognitive approach

to analyzing texts in a global context reveals cultural and social nuances.

3. Analyzing texts in Uzbek with a cognitive approach Studying texts in Uzbek based on a cognitive approach provides the following advantages:

* Cultural semantics: the metaphors of the Uzbek language (for example, "the white way") reflect not only language, but also culture.

• Harmony of language and thinking: in Uzbek, spatial concepts are often expressed in connection with social relations. Example: the phrase "lend a helping hand."

Discussion In the era of globalization and digital technologies, text analysis is not limited to studying the relationships between linguistic units, but also analyzes social and cognitive processes through them. The linguocognitive approach allows for a deeper and broader interpretation of this process.

1. Application in education: A cognitive approach to teaching a foreign language through text analysis can be an effective tool.

2. Digital tools: the usefulness of a cognitive approach to automatic text analysis using NLP algorithms is increasing.

3. Importance in cultural studies: the disclosure of cultural codes through texts is important for determining the place of the Uzbek language on the world stage.

The importance of the linguocognitive approach in text analysis in the era of globalization and digital technologies is invaluable. This approach allows for a

deeper understanding not only of linguistic units, but also of the cultural and cognitive processes that are formed through them. From this point of view, studying the texts of the Uzbek language brings great benefits not only to linguistics, but also to cultural studies and education. In the future, it is necessary to expand the possibilities of studying various aspects of language based on a linguocognitive approach, making extensive use of artificial intelligence technologies and corpus linguistics tools.

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